

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

AN INNOVATIVE SYSTEM OF PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF CHANGES IN THE LIFE CYCLE OF A CONSTRUCTION STAKEHOLDER ENTERPRISE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6980252>

Abstract

The article is devoted to the development of methodological principles for the formation of a process-oriented management system of a construction company-developer based on a business-targeted approach, which involves the transformation of the complex of business goals of the enterprise into the topology of its centers of managerial and executive responsibility in the form of models and regulation of process management, which allows to direct the activities of these creation of value for stakeholders of the construction enterprise. Summarizing the scientific assets on the modeling of changes, different approaches to their management, it is difficult to form one universal model that would clearly and in detail describe the stages of the change process of a modern enterprise. None of the presented change management models is the best and able to adapt to a specific enterprise, because none of them takes into account the real operating conditions of the organization, the behavioral characteristics of this or that employee, etc. It should be borne in mind that depending on the depth and goals of the planned transformations, the current situation at the enterprise, the order of implementation of certain change management actions may be different. Only by taking into account the specifics of the business entity, assessing its capabilities and problem areas, can the order and phasing of planning and implementation of changes be established.

In particular, the issue of developing an updated technology of process-oriented management of construction enterprises as an innovative unifier, formed on the basis of determining the level of their managerial and technological maturity, which will allow to ensure a dynamic level of development within the traditional formats of the economic interests of construction enterprises, is insufficiently researched. There are a number of outstanding issues related to research on maturity modeling and assessment approaches (level of excellence) of process-oriented management systems. The purpose of this work is to develop the theoretical and methodological provisions and applied principles of process-oriented development of construction enterprises aimed at improving the procedural and instrumental basis for making management decisions and substantiating measures to optimize organizational management structures in the conditions of a dynamic business environment for the implementation of investment and construction projects.

Keywords: *change management, business process, process approach to management, strategic planning, business-target approach, enterprise management regulations.*

Under the current conditions of economic development, the processes of operational project management, which include the analysis of problems, determination of priorities and the search for approaches to their solution, are of particular importance. During the operational management of the implementation of development programs, it is necessary to take into account the possibility of crises, which, as a rule, are perceived as something completely unpredictable. Therefore, management and project participants are often not ready for them. At such moments, it is necessary to act quickly and make informed decisions, applying innovative project technologies. It is known that crises, disasters, impasses are all branching points or bifurcation points in the process of program implementation, the approach to which creates a rather dangerous situation.

Sometimes it is not so much the current state of the program implementation process, although it may be at a fairly stable level, but the trend of its future development. One of the signs of approaching an unstable position of the system can be considered, for example, the achievement of the project's maximum value, which corresponds to the growth stage of the life cycle, at

which the appearance of a hidden crisis is most likely, since at this moment there is an inversion of the development trend in the opposite direction. Issues of this type are solved by integrating special methods and models of project management into the current system of management processes for the implementation of "change management" programs.

Today, the operational management of projects and programs requires a clear and timely definition of the necessary organizational changes at each point of bifurcation in order to maintain the effectiveness of their implementation. At the same time, the development program is formed taking into account the estimated duration of the implementation of each of the projects and the latest deadline for the completion of the program tied to a certain bifurcation point [1].

In the table 1 shows typical bifurcation points that may arise during the execution of each stage of program implementation. In the process of preparing the program, interconnected chains of projects appear on certain vision horizons. At each stage, project perspectives are refined and synchronized.

Table 1

Typical bifurcation points of the program implementation process

Name	Characteristic
Market vulnerability	Introducing new products to the market
A crisis of strategy	Changing priorities at different levels of management
Investment crisis	Lack of funds and other resources
Information crisis	Inefficient management of programs and projects
Innovation crisis	Inconsistency of the main elements of the structure
The crisis of the transition to professional management	Loss of efficiency
Crisis of integration	Non-professional project management in organizations within the framework of development programs
Crisis of autonomy	Conflicts in organizations, inability to attract external capital for development
Crisis of organizational relations	Development and implementation of innovations
A crisis of manageability	Unmanageability, decentralization
A crisis of confidence	Reducing the competitiveness of program products and reducing the pace of implementation
Competitiveness crisis	Decreased motivation and loss of flexibility

The main reason for the unstable position of programs is the problems associated with integration processes and development in a competitive environment. One of the obstacles to the successful implementation of projects remains unsatisfactory management, which is not always able to quickly implement and direct corrective actions to negative factors, classifying them as insignificant, not seeking to study and understand the trends of their influence, and the lack of necessary information does not allow effective application of methods of their localization.

As a rule, at such moments, projects implemented within the framework of programs must prove their viability or end. An unstable system in stable time cannot overcome bifurcation points. A significant contrast in such situations is the methods of organizing project

management that take current risks into account. Therefore, it is necessary to develop models of operational response systems, and to create them, you need to use all the available tools of project management [2].

It is known that all stages of the life cycle of program implementation (Fig.1) are formed under the influence of constantly and cumulatively acting laws, such as: the law of supply and demand; the law of price formation of products and technology; quality management law; the law of cost reduction; the law on the development of STP; the law of innovative development, etc. These laws must be taken into account when determining bifurcation points, as well as when developing a system of operational response in case of their occurrence.

Figure 1. Stages of the change management process at the construction enterprise

Depending on the urgency of transformations, previous experience in managing them, the management may combine some stages or change their sequence. Let's consider each of the stages of the change management process in more detail.

The stage of preparation for changes is characterized by the recognition of the company's management

of the need to change the existing situation. That is, the heads (managers) of the enterprise intuitively, or relying on signals coming from the external environment, or reacting to a negative situation that has already developed, make a decision about the need for changes.

At the same time, it is worth noting that stating the need for changes is not enough, their goals and

methods of implementation should be determined. It is appropriate to note that the implementation of changes and their effective management at the current stage is impossible without the formation of a so-called change management team [3].

A group of professionals directly interested in achieving the set goals is formed, where each participant performs a certain managerial role and is responsible for a specific task [4].

At the initial stage, it is advisable to carry out diagnostics of the enterprise, during which the existing potential is evaluated, the competitive position of the enterprise is analyzed and factors indicating the need for changes are made.

The next stage can be "implementation of changes", where it is mandatory to draw up a plan for changes, because the effectiveness of their implementation as a whole depends on how carefully the changes will be planned at the enterprise.

The change plan should reflect the company's development strategy, it is also necessary to identify and assess possible obstacles that may appear on the way to change and apply tools to overcome possible resistance in advance.

The final stage in the change management process is the implementation of the planned changes. An evaluation of the results of the implemented changes is expected from the point of view of economic efficiency and social consequences, etc.

Using the methodology presented in [5-7], we will calculate the life cycle efficiency Δ initially without taking into account the influence of system state change points. The calculation can be represented as the dependence of costs Z and profit P on the time T of its implementation:

$$\Delta = F(P, Z, T), \quad (1)$$

where T is time; Z – costs; P is profit.

At the same time, the profit function $P = f(T)$ and the cost function $Z = \phi(T)$, which are defined on the time segment of the life cycle $T \in [0; T_n]$.

The program life cycle efficiency Δ can be determined by calculating the sum of the cost and profit volumes, denoted by ΔZ and ΔP , respectively. Thus, the amount of costs generated at each stage of the life cycle has different values and can be mathematically expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_z = & -\int_0^{T_1} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_2}^{T_3} \phi(T) dT - \\ & -\int_{T_3}^{T_4} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_4}^{T_5} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_5}^{T_6} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_6}^{T_7} \phi(T) dT - \\ & -\int_{T_7}^{T_8} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_8}^{T_9} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_9}^{T_{10}} \phi(T) dT - \int_{T_{10}}^{T_{11}} \phi(T) dT. \end{aligned}$$

The current economic situation in Ukraine requires a serious revision of the principles and mechanisms of enterprise management. Many construction companies under the influence of changing demand for products and services, methods of production and customer service of construction products are faced with

the need to change their structures. Currently, most construction companies have a strong functional structure, ie they are vertically oriented organizational structures that do not provide, as experience has shown, competitiveness. The current state of the economy of Ukraine is characterized by a high level of uncertainty, increased competition and the spread of globalization processes, as well as a crisis state of almost all branches of the national economy. The following can be considered the main reasons that negatively affect the intensification of construction activities:

- high investment risks, unstable financial condition of a significant number of enterprises and, as a result, low attractiveness of investments in the production sphere for investors;
- credit policy, which caused a lack of interest and incentives to invest bank capital and capital of other financial institutions in the development of the production potential of Ukraine;
- lack of qualified personnel at construction enterprises.

The generalization of information on the state of the construction industry made it possible to identify the following factors of the macroenvironment of structural changes:

- collapse of the construction complex;
- processes of denationalization and privatization;
- tax and depreciation policy;
- credit policy;
- quality of the investment process and investment climate;
- formation of new market niches.

Among the factors of the internal environment that objectively determine the expediency and necessity of structural changes at enterprises of the construction industry, we include:

- unsatisfactory financial condition of a significant number of enterprises;
- conflicts of corporate interests;
- activity planning system;
- use of outdated technologies;
- lack of financing of own technologies for development of large projects;
- outdated material and technical base, lack of working capital.

The very trends of structural changes as consequences of the interaction of macro- and internal environmental factors are formulated as follows: growth of production restructuring processes with reactive and forced nature of changes; lagging in time of real restructuring processes from objective shifts in the market environment; formation of a chain reaction of inhibiting the development of other industries and spheres of activity. Therefore, the establishment of cause-and-effect relationships of factors and their action in the environment of the functioning of enterprises made it possible to state that in the construction industry the issues of feasibility and necessity of restructuring at all levels of enterprise management are considered traditionally narrowly and are mostly reduced to the restructuring of

production (provided that the status of the enterprise as legal entity).

The use of elements of the strategic analysis methodology made it possible to identify the delay in change management processes, which negatively affects the competitiveness of enterprises, their loss of part of the sales markets and, accordingly, the construction of optimistic development scenarios. Such negative phenomena emerged against the background of large-scale processes of denationalization and disintegration of enterprises, as well as other market transformations, which, unfortunately, did not lead to automatic transformation of the pricing mechanism, reduction of the market influence of individual business entities, improvement of the situation on the investment market and its stabilization. In addition, the analysis of tax, credit, and depreciation policy mechanisms showed their inability to timely facilitate the restructuring of business processes, improve the quality of the investment process, update production potential, and does not free enterprises from the problem of their accumulation of outdated and non-working fixed assets.

The conducted study of the macroeconomic environment of enterprises revealed the need to revise the state policy in the construction industry in the direction of forming levers of influence on the activation of restructuring processes, especially with the anticipatory nature of changes. At the micro level, increasing the scientific validity of restructuring processes is associated with the development of the conceptual foundations of its management with an orientation towards an innovative development model, which involves the implementation of anticipatory strategies and an integrated display of the productivity of targeted transformations.

The effectiveness of the implementation of the integration process largely depends on how effectively various forms of interaction of construction enterprises are managed. In conditions when the interaction of enterprises within integrated structures does not bring the desired effects, there is a growing need to update methodical approaches that allow improving the management mechanism of integrated structures. One of the conditions for effective knowledge management in the project is the creation and productive functioning of a communication system that unites the participants of the project implementation.

Functionally oriented company does not stimulate employee interest in the end result. Subdivisions and services in the vertical organizational structure are weakly interconnected, because they are as if in a competitive environment. Separation and solution of problems without their clear coordination with the goals of the organization do not ensure the effectiveness of such a structure, despite the presence of highly qualified specialists. The exchange of information between different units in such structures is extremely difficult, which leads to a sharp decline in management efficiency due to lack of coherence and the necessary interaction in functional units and ultimately to a significant deterioration in economic performance. Most of the business

processes performed in such enterprises are not controlled by anyone and no one is responsible for them, as they are not described or documented.

Process-oriented approach to the management of construction companies allows you to create a structure that provides effective business process management, aimed at continuous improvement of the quality of finished construction products and meet the ever-growing demands of consumers.

Creating systems for effective management of organizations of a very diverse nature and scope - one of the problems facing modern management. There is no universal algorithm for creating such management systems, but it is possible to develop general principles for building business management systems. Among the most advanced methods of building effective management systems, the most popular is the so-called process approach to management, which is to allocate within the organization a network of processes and manage them to achieve organizational efficiency.

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